

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK PHONETIC SYSTEM

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Abstract: This article discusses the language and speech units, analysis of and the specific features of English and Uzbek phonetic system. Moreover, the article considers the etymology of words which were borrowed from different languages and reveals comparison of English with Uzbek languages that has a great influence on the developmental process of English language, phonetic features of English words comparing with Uzbek language by representing examples as well.

Key words: *Phonetics, phoneme, speech units, phonetic system, comparison, word combination, fluency.*

Introduction

One of the primary linguistic components of integrated skills is phonetics. It's not a subject taught in schools. Pronunciation in English is the only language taught widely. When teaching listening, pronouncing words correctly in English is crucial as the foundation of communication is the phoneme.

Language, which consists of phonemes, serves to contact people with others. To learn English pronunciation perfectly, is to learn integrated skills too.¹

To pronounce English phonemes, phonetic combinations, words, sentences, effect understanding of listening, reading speaking as well as oral and written speech. We can see them in the followings:

1. If words are mispronounced, students may misunderstand. And a complete new meaning may appear.

a) white instead of wide

It instead of eat

Pot instead of port

Send instead of sent

b) build as built

Spend as spent

Get as got

¹ Хошимов Ў, Ёкубов И. Инглиз тили ўқитиш методикаси- Шарк, 2003, в.74

It may fluently to the meanings of words. After listening incorrectly, students may understand another meaning. Students should know stress, rhythm, tone in order to pronounce correctly.

For example: 1. Good ↓ morning

2. Good ↑ morning

Both examples have the same meaning. On the first, we can understand simple and frankly greeting.

And the second, greeting with irony or saying Good bye

If students mispronounce or mishear, it affects their writings too. Especially, it's important to write dictations correctly.

For schools, educational projects are launched. According to the projects, ample of demands:²

1. English vowels, consonants phonemes and their pronunciation;
2. To pronounce vowels long and short
3. To compare Uzbek phonemes with English phonemes;
4. The structure of system of syllables
5. Word stress, tones;
6. To part sentences into sintagmas;
7. To teach reductions of vowels;

While, we are comparing phonetic systems of two languages, we should consider their specific features.

These features may have positive and negative effects. Positive effects may help to learn pronunciation easily.

For negative affects students come across interferential problems, at the result, they confuse .

It's teachers` job to choose suitable methods, means styles in order not to made mistakes. But not all methods have the same results. These are chosen according to the students` age, their ability and course.

English phonetic system has its own specific features³. They are:

1. Every vowel is expressed four sounds. (It means that six vowels are pronounced with 20 sounds)
- 2) Sounds are more than letters; 26 letters but 40 sounds;
- 3) Existence of diphthongs
- 4) Two letters means a sound [ʃ and tʃ]
- 5) Short-long sounds: i[i:], e[eə]

² Хошимов Ў.Ёкубов И. Инглиз тили ўқитиш методикаси-Т: Шарк , 2003,в75

³, Хошимов Ў.Ёкубов И. Инглиз тили ўқитиш методикаси- Шарк , в76

Every phoneme in relation to the other phoneme may be characterized by this distinctive and non-distinctive feature. Thus, a phoneme is a bundle of distinctive features. In relation to the phoneme the same phoneme's allophones have non-distinctive feature such as the relation between /p/ aspirated and /p/ non-aspirated may be characterized by a non-distinctive feature. But the common features of /p / and /p/ generalize the phoneme /p/ which is bilabial, plosive-occlusive, voiceless.⁴

As a linguistic unit the phoneme functions to distinguish lexical and grammatical forms and in this way performs its communicative function in a language. Every phoneme with its allophones is a member of a phonological opposition.

The exact number of the phonemes also called the inventory of the phoneme which exists in a certain language is established by using the method of commutation. This method is defined as substitution or replacing one speech sound by another in the same position of minimal pairs of words. For example: pet-bet-set-let-net-jet-vet.

Sometimes it is very difficult to discover minimal pairs. It is possible to find a few minimal pairs but no minimal pair exists for the opposition but if there is no minimal pair in the language we must not omit the phoneme from the inventory. Such as in Russian and borrowed from it in Uzbek the phoneme cannot be used in minimal pairs but we describe it as a special phoneme which has limited distribution. By the term distribution we mean all the positions and combinations in which a certain speech sound – a representative of the phoneme is used. There are four types of distribution.⁵

1. If two elements cannot be used in the same position and replace other in one position they are considered to be in a complementary distribution. For example, aspirated /p,t,k/ sounds can be used only before stressed vowels if they are not preceded by /s/ and in the intervocalic position. But in all other positions non-aspirated/p,t,k/ sounds are used. Thus /p,t,k,/ sounds cannot replace /p,t,k/ sounds in the same position. They represent the allophones of the /p,t,k/ phonemes. It is possible to establish the allophones of the phoneme using complementary distribution.
2. Two elements (sounds) may be used in one and the same position and serve to distinguish the words. For example, bill /bil/-till/til/, sight/sait/ -bight/bait/ -night/nait/ -right/rait/-light /lait / -might/mait/ etc.

⁴ Abduazizov A.A English phonetics A theoretical course-T,-2007.p.6

⁵ Abduazizov A.A English phonetics A theoretical course-T,-2007.p28

Using contrast distribution, it is possible to establish the number of phonemes in a given language.

3. The elements (sounds) used in one and the same position and which cannot distinguish the meanings of words are considered to be in free variation. In such cases every sound manifests the free allo-phone of the phoneme. This type of distribution is known also as an equivalent distribution. For example, some speakers pronounce /e/ sound either half -close/e/ or half-open /e/ in one and the same position but it cannot distinguish the words.

4. Two various sounds may be in one and the same position. In such cases one of the sounds represents the free allophone of the other. For example, the word phonetics may be pronounced as / fonetics/, /founetics/ and /fenetics/ where the sounds /o/, /e/ represent the free allophones of the phoneme /ou/. In reality each of them is an allophone of the separate phoneme.

The distributional method is very important in phonological analysis of the sound structure. It is necessary to show also what clusters of sounds the pattern of a language admits. The branch of phonology which studies the possible clusters of sounds in words and morphemes is known as “phonotactics”.

Using the statistical method, it is possible to establish the exact number of phonological oppositions in a language and the number of sound clusters in initial, medial and final positions of the words. For example, in English, out of a theoretically possible 11,000 initial three member consonantal clusters at the beginning of a syllable, only about 40 occur. Of 576 possible combinations of two consonants, only 137 are utilized by the language. There are no initial three member consonantal clusters in Uzbek. Thus it is difficult to teach the Uzbek students the pronunciation of the initial three member consonantal clusters of English.⁶

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